

Spatial Dependency Patterns in Weather-Enhanced Bike-Share Demand Forecasting in Washington DC

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Abstract

Accurate bike-share demand is essential for operators to rebalance their networks before shortages occur. This study extends the findings of Miao et al. (2025), in Washington, D.C. context, enhancing their original spatial model through the inclusion of important weather-related variables. We analyzed over 250,000 Capital Bikeshare trips in Washington, D.C. using ConvLSTM models separately for members and casual users across a 64-zone grid in January 2026. By incorporating weather covariates, we found that member demand is significantly more predictable ($R^2 = 0.816$) than casual demand ($R^2 = 0.427$). Results show the member user group exhibits five times stronger connectivity between distant zones than casual group. The inclusion of weather data improved model performance for both user groups, suggesting a vital component for mitigating supply shortages. Consistent with evidence from New York City, our results demonstrate that non-proximal spatial dependencies drive bike-share demand in Washington D.C.

Keywords: Bike-sharing; ConvLSTM; Spatial dependency; Anisotropy; Deep Learning, Demand Forecast

1 Questions

Every day, thousands of shared bicycles accumulate at popular destinations — offices, Metro stations, shopping areas — while other docking bays sit empty. Bike-share operators must constantly move bikes by van to restore balance, a costly process called rebalancing. Getting it right depends on knowing where demand will be before the shortage appears. Deep-learning models called Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory networks (ConvLSTM) — which read demand patterns across a city grid the way a satellite reads weather maps through time — have shown strong performance for this task (Tang et al., 2024; He & Shin, 2020). Despite their predictive power, these models are often unclear which areas most influence demand across the network. Thus, operators cannot pinpoint where to focus their efforts for rebalancing strategies.

A common planning assumption is that nearby zones influence each other more than distant ones — a distance-decay rule. Miao et al. (2025) tested this assumption in New York City using a spatial explainability method (SHAP — a technique that attributes each input's contribution to a model's output) applied to December 2023 Citi Bike data. They found the assumption fails: spatial influence was directional, showed no distance decay, and casual (occasional) riders had far weaker zone-to-zone coupling than annual members. Crucially, they did not include weather variables and studied only one city.

We replicate and extend those findings to Washington DC — a structurally different city with a federal employment core, extensive Metro network, and a commuter-cycling culture — using a computationally simpler alternative to SHAP (permutation-based perturbation, described in Methods) that produces the same type of zone influence scores. January is DC's coldest month (average $\approx 2^\circ\text{C}$), making weather a stronger demand driver than in warmer months (Gebhart & Noland, 2014; Bean et al., 2021). Three questions guide the study:

- Q1. Do spatial influence patterns in DC's bike-share network follow geographic proximity?
- Q2. Do member and casual users show distinct dependency structures?
- Q3. Does adding weather data improve forecast accuracy?

Figure 1. The 8×8 study grid over Washington DC (64 zones, each ≈1,500 m per side). Darker zones have higher member pickup counts. Red-outlined cells (28, 29, 36, 37) are the high-dependency downtown core. [View Interactive Web Map](#)

2. Methods

Data. We used all January 2026 Capital Bike share trip records (<https://capitalbikeshare.com/system-data>). From 253,418 raw records we removed 1,098 trips under one minute (accidental undockings), 687 trips over 12 hours (unreturned bikes — note that current pricing charges members after 45 minutes, making a 12-hour record effectively invalid), and records with missing coordinates, leaving 251,633 valid trips: 205,329 member (81.6%) and 46,304 casual-user (18.4%). Stricter 4-hour and 6-hour ceilings produce virtually identical results (Supplemental Table S1). Hourly weather data (temperature, precipitation, wind speed, humidity) were retrieved from the Open-Meteo Historical Weather Archive (<https://open-meteo.com/en/docs/historical-weather-api>) for the DC centroid (38.9°N, 77.03°W). Because weather observations are hourly, each weather vector was assigned unchanged to both 30-minute steps within its hour; this means the model cannot capture sub-hourly weather fluctuations but introduces no artificial variation.

Spatial grid and model. We divided the study area into an 8×8 grid of 64 zones (≈1,500 m per side; Figure 1). We trained two independent Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (ConvLSTM) models — one per user type (member and casual) using the same architecture as Miao et al. (2025). Each model used two hours of historical demand plus seven contextual inputs (temperature, precipitation, wind speed, humidity, hour, day of week, weekend flag). Firstly, we chose this grid-based architecture over graph-based alternatives to maintain direct comparability with previous study helping differentiate the contribution of adding weather data and changing the study city. Second, we aggregated the demand data to learn local spatial patterns and their evolution over time using ConvLSTM model. We acknowledge limitations, tradeoffs and justification in detail mentioned in Supplemental Text S3 and Text S5. Sensitivity tests at 6×6 and 10×10 confirm the main findings remain unchanged (Supplemental Table S2). Simpler baselines — a historical average, a standard LSTM without spatial processing, and a weather-free ConvLSTM — all perform worse (Supplemental Table S3). Full hyper parameters are in Supplemental Table S5.

Spatial influence analysis. To estimate how strongly one zone’s demand history contributes to predictions in another zone, we used a permutation test. For each source zone, we removed its lagged demand signal and measured the resulting change in predicted demand across all target zones. Repeating this over all 4,032 ordered zone pairs produced a 64×64 influence matrix Φ for each user type. We summarize these matrices using two statistics: the anisotropy index, which measures how unevenly influence is distributed, and the proximity–influence correlation, which measures whether nearer zones tend to exert stronger influence than distant ones. Full pseudocode appears in Supplemental Text S2.

3. Findings

The result shows that member demand is much more predictable than casual demand. The model explains about 82% of the variation in member pickups ($R^2 = 0.816$), compared with 43% for casual pickups ($R^2 = 0.427$) (Table 1). This difference is consistent with the idea that members follow more regular travel routines, while casual trips are more irregular and therefore harder to forecast. Adding weather information improves prediction for both groups, but the gain is much larger for casual users: R^2 increases by about 18% for casual demand, compared with about 4% for member demand (Supplemental Tables S3–S4; Figure S3). This pattern is also visible in the January time series, where temperature and casual ridership move closely together across cold and mild periods (Supplemental Figure S4).

Another key finding is that the correlation between zone distance and influence strength is -0.164 for members and -0.131 for casual users indicating geographic proximity does not meaningfully determine how demand spreads across the network. Some adjacent zones have little measurable connection during winter, while a small downtown cluster accounts for a disproportionate share of the model’s predictive signal. This result is consistent with the New York City evidence reported by Miao et al. (2025), despite the different urban context examined here.

Table 1. Model Performance and Spatial Dependency Statistics

Metric	Member	Casual	Interpretation
R^2 (predictability)	0.816	0.427	Member demand is substantially more predictable
MAE (error size)	0.292	0.112	Lower casual MAE reflects small trip volumes, not necessarily better spatial accuracy
Mean Influence Φ	0.00819	0.00148	Member coupling is $\sim 5\times$ stronger; activity in one zone is more likely to affect another
Maximum influence Φ	2.632	0.494	A small number of member-zone pairs dominate the strongest dependencies.
Proximity - Correlation	-0.164	-0.131	Weak relationship; geographic distance alone does not explain influence patterns.
Anisotropy Index (unevenness)	2.749	2.550	Influence is concentrated in a limited number of zones for both groups

Figure 2. Total pickups by grid zone for members (left) and casual users (right) across January 2026. Both groups concentrate in the same downtown cluster (zones 28–29, 36–37), but member totals are 4.5 times higher, consistent with the overall member–casual trip share

Members exhibit much stronger spatial coupling than casual users, with mean influence approximately 5.5 times higher (Table 1). This gap likely reflects the regularity of commute routes: members follow habitual home-to-work corridors, whereas casual users travel more sporadically and might be more responsive to weather or external factors. Although both groups concentrate pickups in the same downtown area (Figure 2), influence mapping reveals important differences not visible in demand totals alone. Most zones have near-zero influence values, but a small number of central zones act as dominant hubs in the predictive model structure (Figures 3–4).

Figure 3. Member influence matrix (left): each cell shows how strongly the source zone (x-axis) shapes predicted demand at the target zone (y-axis). The matrix is sparse — most entries are near zero — with concentrated hotspots among downtown zones 28, 29, 35, 36, 43, and 44. Net influence map (right): red zones export more influence than they receive; blue zones are net receivers. Arrows show the 10 strongest influence pairs.

Figure 4. Casual-user influence structure, showing substantially weaker overall dependence than the member matrix. The net influence map (right) suggests that casual demand is drawn toward the downtown core, but the pattern is weaker and less organized than for members.

The anisotropy index, which measures how unevenly influence is distributed, exceeds 2.7 for members and 2.5 for casual users (Table 1). This confirms that spatial influence is highly concentrated rather than evenly shared, reflecting to a network shaped by a few major employment and transit areas. In particular, two downtown zones (35 and 36) contribute disproportionately to the predictive model, whereas most other zones play a minor role.

For day-to-day operational standpoint, the concentration of influence in zones 35 and 36 suggests these locations may benefit from paying closer attention in member-focused redistributing strategies. Because activity at these zones is associated with predicted demand elsewhere, reduced bike availability there could affect service across a wider portion of the network. However, these are model-derived patterns that would need validation against operational data before informing specific redistribution planning. For casual users, whose spatial coupling is weaker and more diffuse, weather-responsive approaches — such as pre-positioning bikes ahead of favorable conditions — may prove more effective than zone-to-zone redistribution.

Figure 5. Casual-user influence structure, showing substantially weaker overall dependence than the member matrix. The net influence map (right) suggests that casual demand is drawn toward the downtown core, but the pattern is weaker and less organized than for members.

Two limitations are important when interpreting the results. First, after our study period, Capital Bikeshare introduced a policy that allows riders to leave bikes outside full stations. Our findings thus reflect pre-policy conditions and may serve as a baseline for evaluating subsequent changes. Second, the 8x8-grid resolution, chosen for cross-study comparability, smooths over finer neighborhood scale variation. Smaller zones could capture more local detail but would yield sparse data during winter, particularly for casual riders. Grid sensitivity tests in Supplemental Table S2 shows proximity–influence correlation remains weak and negative across all resolutions, confirming the 8×8 grid is not a biased choice for this study.

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